

BOOK REVIEW

A Review of *Family and Clan in North East India: Reflections by Christian Scholars*
Alphonsus D'Souza, Lalnghakthumi, and Pangernungba Kechu (Editors)
Guwahati: North Eastern Social Research Centre, 2015.

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The present book is a compilation of the papers presented during the seminar on *Family and Clan in Tribal Societies of North East India* jointly organised by North Eastern Social Research Centre (NESRC), Guwahati, and Tribal Study Centre (TSC), Eastern Theological Centre, Jorhat on 26-27 June 2014 at Guwahati, Assam. This compilation aims to capture the changes that are taking place in family, clan, and social organisation in the tribal communities of North East India from the perspective of native Christian scholars belonging to various Christian denominations. Furthering its objectives, the book also attempts to relook at the core values of traditional tribal worldviews that are in tune with the Christian values while not losing sight of the newer realities (p. iii).

This volume, consisting of 15 scholarly papers, focuses on enriching the understanding of the faith among the tribal societies of North East India. In addition, all the authors are native scholars of the region and mostly deal with their own tribes. The papers in the book are arranged under three broad themes: 'Situation of the Family and Clan in Some Tribal Societies', 'Understanding, Theological Reflections, and Suggestions for Family Ministry or Family Apostolate in Some Tribal Societies', and 'Gender Issues and the Position & Role of Women in Some Tribal Societies' (p. xiii).

The first theme includes four papers which deal with the situation of the family and clan existing in some tribal societies of North East India. The

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first paper by Janet Florine Tellison 'Kinship, Marriage, and Family among the Riang of Tripura' looks at the traditional social structures and evolving patterns of the *Riangs*, the second largest tribal community in the state of Tripura. It also seeks to understand the dynamics and identify the factors responsible for change in *Riang* kinship, marriage, and family. She notes that traditional *Riang* social institutions such as marriage, family, and kinship have considerably weakened owing to the introduction of formal education, gainful employment outside the family, and new religious practices.

The changing social structure is further emphasised in the paper by Nokhwenu Kharütso entitled 'The Angami Family at the Crossroads' against the backdrop of changing family system. She attempts to identify the changes taking place in *Angami Naga* society through a comparative analysis of traditional and contemporary *Angami* societies. She mentions that traditional *Angami* family was an autonomous, self-sufficient unit. However, the situation has changed due to numerous factors such as: coming of the Britishers, introduction of Christianity, introduction of modern education, and changes in traditional economy.

In the third paper, entitled 'Clan and Family in Khasi Society,' Shanba Hayong has been critical of the role of various factors for rapid erosion of *Khasi* traditional values. The paper argues that the roles and functions of clan and family in the present-day *Khasi* society are significantly weakened due to the impact of modernisation, secularisation, and westernisation coupled with the influence of information technology in the present globalised world. He calls for rediscovering and reinterpreting the cultural values that are liberal, life-affirming, and accommodative and for making them relevant to the needs of the different sections of the community.

Linus Neli's paper 'Marriage and Family in the Mao Community' explores the impact of the twin processes of Christianity and modernity on *Mao Naga* tribe through the analysis of some challenges the community faces today in terms of marriage and establishment of stable families and transmission of faith and culture to younger generation. His paper raises a few pertinent concerns for further reflection: the need to understand the substantive transition that has taken place from pre-Christian era to post-modern Christianity in *Mao* society; to study whether the *Mao* community has become weaker or stronger in contemporary time; to identify the factors of unresolved crises in this time

of transition and the challenges posed by the present situation; and in the context of socio-cultural and religious transition, how to regulate Church marriages and faith education to our children.

The second theme, namely, ‘Understanding, Theological Reflections, and Suggestions for Family Ministry or Family Apostolate in Some Tribal Societies’ includes seven papers which delve deeper into the understanding of the family and clan in some tribal societies of North East India and offer theological reflections and suggestions for family ministry or family apostolate in these societies.

In the first paper ‘The Role of Culture, State, and Faith in the Formation of Apatani Christian Community,’ Rimi Tadu elaborates the dialectical role played by culture, faith, and the state in the evolution of the *Apatani* Christian community. She observes that the *Apatani* Christian community is still rudimentary in several aspects and this irregularity gives a unique reflexive opportunity to create a culture of its own. Her concern is the paradoxical challenge for the community like the one faced by the education policy of transforming or preserving the age-old traditions of the *Apatanis* and of finding a suitable place for them in the larger community.

The second paper by Francis Sebastian, titled ‘Rebuilding Familial Values of the *Yimchungrii Nagas*,’ draws on the experiences of the *Yimchungrii Nagas* in rebuilding and rediscovering family values through Christianity. He argues that in the process of embracing Christianity, the *Yimchungrii* abandoned many elements of their traditional culture, songs, dances, and important practices (p. 121). However, he also asserted that many of those values and ideals are in tune with the Biblical and Christian traditions; and hence, need to be recaptured, appreciated, and made a part of Christian life.

Peter Haokip, in his paper ‘Traditional Kuki Family: An ‘Anonymous’ Christian Family,’ describes the traditional *Kuki* family as the ideal Christian family, for its identity and well-being come from being in fellowship with others in peace and harmony. The next four papers under this theme deal with the need for tribal evangelism, pastoral challenges, and theological reflections in some of the tribes of North Eastern states. Some aspects of these papers include a need for evangelism in *Munda* tribe of Assam by Michael Herenz,

pastoral challenge in *Dimasa* family structure by Nilesh Parmar, and the theological reflections of family and clan system in *Miz̧o* and *AoNaga* societies by Lalnghakthuami and Limatula Longkumer, respectively.

The last theme of ‘Gender Issues and the Position & Role of Women in Some Tribal Societies’ includes four papers that largely focus on gender issues, especially the position and role of tribal women in a few tribal communities of North East Indian region.

The first of them, ‘The Role of Karbi Christian Women in the Family, Church, and Society: A Theological Reflection’ presented by Luke Rongphar, stresses the contribution of *Karbi* Christian women to the family, Church, and society. He observes that, despite the major contributions of the *Karbi* Christian women, their role and involvement in active politics are insignificant when put in comparison with non-Christian *Karbi* women. To put them at par with non-Christian *Karbi* women, he calls for evolving and maintaining Christian spirit, cultivating good moral character, and generating testimony to help build a better society free of corruption and injustice.

Lalrinawmi Ralte’s paper on ‘The Bride Price System: Tribal Women’s Critical Evaluation’ observes the relationship between the *Miz̧o* customary laws and bride price system in *Miz̧o* society from the perspective of women. She argues that the bride price system along with marriage practices in *Miz̧o* women’s life makes them second-class citizens in the society that perceives them as commodities to be “bought and sold” (p. 156). She stresses that unless oppressive customs and traditions are abolished and unless their legal rights in the family are assured, equality cannot be a reality for *Miz̧o* women.

In the third paper, ‘Tribal Theology and Status of Women,’ Amrit Kumar Goldsmith traces the changes in the status of women since 1836 in the history of Christianity introduced by the American missionaries in North East India (the then Assam). Through this paper, he observes that the opportunities created for women’s education in the Christian era paved the way for girls to access all sorts of education and to do well in various fields. The next paper on ‘Christianity and Khasi Matrilineal Women of Meghalaya’ by O. L. Snaitang also provides a somewhat similar viewpoint on the impact of Christianity on role and status of tribal women. The author looks at the impact of Christianity on the *Khasi* matrilineal culture in general and women in particular. The author concludes his paper from three developmental perspectives. Firstly,

he notes that while women in the past enjoyed significant privileges in terms of lineage, custodianship, and free movement, they were denied leadership roles. Secondly, he finds that the new administrative policy introduced by British colonial administration gave some relief to women in the clan and family system. Finally, the author observes that Christianity played a vital role in the emancipation of women through education and facilitated their employment both in the church's institutions and government offices.

It is difficult to make a one-dimensional conclusion on the family and clan systems in the tribal societies of North East India owing to their unique features and histories. All the societies have varied family and clan organisations as foundational features of personal and ethnic identity.

Some of the authors deal with the traditional family and clan systems; while others identify the changes that have taken place owing to modernisation and globalisation. Identified factors of change are: British rule and administration, embracing of Christianity, introduction of modern education, and monetisation of the tribal economy. The authors, in general, agree that there has been a weakening of clan system and the rise of the nuclear family along with a decline in communitarian values and rapid development of individualism. Due to this changing scenario, some authors call for considering the "theology of family as the domestic church or as a partnership" to rediscover and return to important traditional values such as communitarian life, caring of the weak, and showing concern for the needy.

This book provides an understanding of traditional family and clan systems in a multi-cultural setting of tribal societies and a multidisciplinary framework of the issues. The book is a collection of multifaceted research papers which are both theoretical and empirical in nature. This volume further provides an opportunity for discussion on issues related to family, clan, and status of women in the contemporary social context. It will also provide a framework for empirical exercises to be carried out with respect to above issues in different parts of the world.

All in all, the papers in the book are rich in content and offer significant insights into the family and clan systems of the tribal societies in North East India. This compilation makes an important contribution to Tribal Studies in general and Tribal Theology in particular.